

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326781690>

Seismic Vulnerability of Steel Frames with Different Bracing Systems

Article in *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* · September 2016

CITATION

1

READS

189

4 authors, including:

Raghu K Raghu

Sri Jagadguru Chandrasekaranathaswamiji Institute of Technology

8 PUBLICATIONS 10 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Dr G Narayana

Sri Jagadguru Chandrasekaranathaswamiji Institute of Technology

5 PUBLICATIONS 7 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Bracing Systems [View project](#)

dia grids [View project](#)

Seismic Vulnerability of Steel Frames with Different Bracing Systems

Nanda Kumar H¹, Shashi Kumar N V², Raghu K³, Dr. G Narayana⁴

¹M.Tech in Structural Engineering, Department of Civil Engineering, SJCIT, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, SJCIT, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, SJCIT, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India

⁴Professor & Head, Department of Civil Engineering, SJCIT, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India

Abstract: *In this postulation the Non linear push over investigation is done for skyscraper steel outline working with various examples of propping frameworks. There are "n" quantities of conceivable outcomes to mastermind steel bracings, for example, Diagonal, Cross, Knee, V, Inverted V or chevron and worldwide sort concentric bracings. An average G+15 - story standard steel outline building is investigated for different sorts of concentric bracings like Diagonal, V, cross, and Exterior X and Performance of every edge is helped out through nonlinear static examination. Mode shapes, Story drift, Base shear, Pushover curve and Performance purpose of every model are done with various examples of supporting frameworks. Three sorts of segment i.e. ISMB, ISMC and ISA area are utilized to thought about for same example of bracings. The Aim of study was to think about the aftereffects of seismic examination of skyscraper steel outline working with various examples of bracings and without propping frameworks*

Keywords: Mode shapes, Story drift, Base shear, Pushover curve

1. Introduction

For the most part, a great many individuals lose their lives because of tremors in various parts of the earth. Tremor is a characteristic wonder, which be produced inside earth outside layer. Seismic tremor be a rapid stun on the Earth's surface. It is quaking in addition to shaking at the plane of the earth coming about because of underground development all along a fault plane of or as of volcanic movement. Seismic tremors be amongst the capable occasions on top of the earth, plus their outcomes be able to startle.

Seismic tremor ground movements be the the majority risky regular dangers wherever together living and financial misfortunes happen. Tremors are normal calamities of a for the most part erratic nature. Term of seismic tremor is generally rather short, enduring from few moments to over a moment or something like that. Building breakdown or harms are the significant misfortunes because of seismic tremor ground movement. Tremor can bring about harm not just by virtue of vibrations which results from them additionally because of other chain impacts like avalanches, surges, fires and so on. The basic impact going on the structure will be anticipated via the floor developments on the area of the structure, despite the fact that the impact of the shudder is measured as far as the vitality discharge at the area of the ground flaw.

Quake designing has made some amazing progress since its introduction to the world and it appears to become quickly as we pick up experience. Every time a tremor happens, something new is accessible to learn. In this way, outline of structure to oppose moderate to serious quake ground movement relying upon the site area is essential. The commonly happening vertical loads i.e. dead load and live

load, don't posture quite a bit of an issue yet the lateral loads because of quake tremors involves incredible anxiety and require extraordinary thought in the configuration of such structures.

Lateral stability have been dependably to one of noteworthy issue of structure particularly inside that zones by means of far above the ground tremor danger this subject has been concentrated on concentric, eccentric and knee supporting bracing systems has recommended in addition to subsequently utilized through structural designers. Inelastic execution be distinct in primary variables impacting their decision on the way to supporting bracing systems. The supporting bracing systems so as to have a more artificial miss happening before breakdown can assimilate more vitality amid the quake

1.1 Objectives

Taking after be principle destinations of there study:

- 1) To carry out non linear static Pushover investigation designed to steel frames utilizing E-tabs programming toward ponder the seismic execution of frames.
- 2) To comprehend the seismic execution of a high rise steel frames working through various examples of bracings, for example, Diagonal, V, Inverted V or chevron, and X utilizing Nonlinear Static Pushover investigation strategy.
- 3) To assess execution elements designed for steel frames among different bracing courses of action intended for various section.
- 4) To comprehend the seismic execution for high rise steel frame working by way of various steel members.

2. Non Linear Static Analysis

2.1 Introduction

Nonlinear static investigation, has been produced in the course of recent years and has turned into the favored examination system for outline and seismic execution assessment purposes as the method is generally basic and considers post flexible conduct. In any case, the system includes certain approximations and rearrangements that some measure of variety is constantly anticipated that would exist in seismic interest expectation of pushover analysis.

2.2 Capacity curve

A general limit for an building relies scheduled upon that quality with distortion limits of the entity segments of the structures. So as toward decide limits past as far as possible, some type of nonlinear examination is required. This strategy utilizes consecutive flexible investigation, superimposed to rough constrain dislodging chart of the general structures. The numerical model of the structures are changed headed for represent decreased conflict of elastic parts. A horizontal force circulation was over connected in anticipation of extra parts defer.

Figure 4.3 Capacity Curve

2.3 Demand curve

Seismic movement amid a seismic tremor produces complex flat dislodging designs which may change with time. Following this movement at each time venture to decide basic configuration prerequisites is judge unfeasible. In support of a known structure with a seismic movement, relocation requests be evaluation of the most extreme probable reaction of the working amid the seismic movement. This curve is a representation of the tremor seismic movement.

Figure 4.4 Demand Curve

2.4 Performance point

Performance point know how to obtain via superimposing capacity spectrum and demand spectrum and at junction point of these two curves is performance point.

Figure 4.5 Superimposing Demand Spectrum and Capacity Spectrum.

3. Structural Modelling

3.1 Introduction

In support of an investigation job, twenty two models of skyscraper steel outline structure (G+15) floors be finished just before sensible conduct for working amid seismic tremor. A dimensions structure was 24m and width is 12m. Those segments were thought, altered by base. Non Linear static investigation that were push over investigation was utilized

3.2 Studied Structural Configuration

Taking after two sorts of basic design is examined.

- 1) G+14 Steel Framed structure without supporting (MRF)
- 2) G+14 Steel Framed structure with various supporting examples Note:

ITotal 22 models are broke down in the study. One exposed edge model.

Four models of ISMB Section. Four models of ISA Section. Four models of ISMC Section

Figure 3.1: Plan of High rise Building Frame

Table 3.1: Building Description

Serial Number	Building Description	
1	Zone	V
2	Zone Factor	0.36
3	Response Reduction Factor	5
4	Importance Factor	1
5	Height of Building	45 m
6	Column Details	ISMB 600
7	Beam Details	ISMB 450
8	Bracing Details-1	ISMB 300
9	Bracing Details 2	ISA 200 x200 x15
10	Bracing Details 3	ISMC 300
11	Thickness of Slab	125 mm
12	Floor to Floor Height	3.0 m
13	Grade of Steel Section	Fe - 250
14	Grade of Concrete	M20
15	Floor Finish	1.5 kN/m ²
16	Live Load	3.0 kN/m ²

Figure 3.2: Exterior X Bracing

Figure 3.4: Diagonal Bracing

Figure 3.3: V Bracing

Figure 3.5: Knee Bracing

Figure 3.6: Bare Frame

Figure 3.7: X Bracing

4. Results and Discussions

Figure 4.1: Joint Displacement

From chart it is experimental that the displacement at roof level of the steel frame structure for V-Brace, Diagonal Brace, X-Brace, decreased up to 13-38 % as compared with bare frame model, whereas in Exterior X-Brace maximum displacement reduced up to 51 % as compared with bare frame model and ISA 200x200x15 Section reduces more displacement compare to ISMC300 and ISMB300 section for similar type of brace

Figure 4.2: Pushover curves of ISMB Sections

From chart the V-Brace, Diagonal Brace, X-Brace models of ISMB Sections models has got more performance displacement and less performance base shear compared to bare frame. Exterior X-Brace model got more stiffness compare to other bracings and it also gives more stiffness compared to angle and channel section.

Figure 4.3: Pushover curves of ISA Sections

From chart the V-Brace, Diagonal Brace, X-Brace models of ISA Sections has got more performance displacement and less performance base shear compared to bare frame. Exterior X-Brace model got more stiffness compare to other bracings

Figure 4.4: Pushover curves of ISMC Sections

Figure 4.6: Performance curves of ISA Sections

From chart the V-Brace, Diagonal Brace, X-Brace models of ISMC Sections has got more performance displacement and less performance base shear compared to bare frame. Exterior X-Brace model got more stiffness compare to other bracings

From chart the Exterior X Brace model have increased performance level compare to other bracing models and it can also be seen that the frames with bracings have lesser vulnerability compared to the frames without bracings.

Figure 4.5: Performance curves of ISMB Sections

From chart the Exterior X Brace model have increased performance level compare to other bracing models and it can also be seen that the frames with bracings have lesser vulnerability compared to the frames without bracings.

Figure 4.7: Performance curves of ISMC Sections

From chart the Exterior X Brace model have increased performance level compare to other bracing models and it can also be seen that the frames with bracings have lesser vulnerability compared to the frames without bracings.

5. Conclusion

1. From displacement chart, watched that removal of rooftop level for steel frame building designed to V-Brace, Diagonal Brace and X-Brace lessens 70%-80% was contrasted and

bare frame model. Though at outside X-Brace, most extreme uprooting diminishes up to 92% as contrasted and uncovered edge model. ISMC Section diminishes more uprooting contrasted with ISA and ISMB segment by around 2% for outside X bracing.

2. From Pushover charts it was watched to bare frame have get extra execution uprooting and fewer execution base shear while contrasted with further models. It know how to be watch that bracings include expanded height of execution together as far as base shear conveying limit and rooftop removal. The V-Brace, Diagonal Brace and X-Brace models comprise a smaller amount execution dislodging and additional execution base shear contrasted with bare frame and Exterior X-Brace model have less execution removal and added execution base shear contrasted with other propping models and ISMB Section give further firmness contrasted with ISA and ISMC area pro comparative sort of bracings.

3. From the Performance tables and diagrams, was watched to capacity and demand curves were plotted pro steel frames with as well as with no bracings in support of seismic zone 5. Exterior X Brace model has shown expanded execution rank when contrasted with other bracing models ,it could likewise exist see so as to bracings contain lesser defenselessness contrasted with as well as without bracings. ISMB Section give further Performance point contrasted with ISA and ISMC comparable sort for bracing.

4. The general Performance Level of every single supporting model be establish amid B-IO (Immediate Occupancy). That hinge status plus area contain resolute, here was noticed to a large portion of the hinges be framed in A-B range.

5. Pushover examination is a decent way to deal with evaluate the sufficiency of a structure to seismic loading.

5.1 Scope for Future Work

- 1) Pushover examination for steel confined structures able to more deliberate utilizing 3D unpredictable arrangement model.
- 2) Pushover examination was done utilizing client characterized hinge properties.
- 3) Pushover examination results could be contrasted and time history investigation results.
- 4) Comparable study could be completed utilizing different sorts of bracings.
- 5) Similar studies can be completed to learn the improved area of bracings.
- 6) Comparable study could be completed in utilizing further Indian Standard areas.
- 7) Pushover examination done pro infilled frames.
- 8) Dissimilar sorts of lateral load examples are able to attempted in pushover examination.

References

- [1] **K.K.Sangle, K.M.Bajori, V.Mhalungkar., 2012** “Seismic analysis of high rise steel frame building with and without bracing” Mumbai.

- [2] **M.D. Kevadkar, P.B. Kodag,(2013)**, “ lateral load analysis of RCC building”
- [3] **Mohammad EyniKangavar.,(2012)**, Modelled a 1bay, 2D, 10 storey RC frame in ETABS by comparing a Knee Braced Frame and Concentric Braced Frame by static method.
- [4] **HaroonRasheedTamboli&Umesh N. Karadi (2012)**, Performed seismic analysis using Equivalent Lateral Force Method for different reinforced concrete (RC) frame building models that included bare frame, in filled frame and open first storey frame.
- [5] **Srikhanta Prasad, et al, (2009)**, presented an analytical study to evaluate nonlinear seismic performance of one bay and two bay RC frames at different storey levels.